

Received / Makale Geliş Tarihi 04.11.2025
Published / Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.01.2026
Volume (Issue) Cilt (Sayı) 10 (62)
pp / ss 01-13

Research Article / Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.18445383
Mail: editor@pejoss.com

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Hüseyin Akar
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0453-6465>
Kilis 7 Aralık University, Kilisli Muallim Rifat Faculty of Education, Kilis / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/048b6qs33>

The Mediating Role of Organizational Dissent and Organizational Inertia in the Relationship Between Fear Culture and Organizational Blindness: Evidence from Schools

Korku Kültürü ile Örgütsel Körlük Arasındaki İlişkide Örgütsel Muhalefet ve Örgütsel Ataletin Aracılık Rolü: Okullardan Bulgular

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the mediating effects of organizational dissent and organizational inertia on the relationship between fear culture and organizational blindness in schools. In contemporary educational institutions, which must adapt to rapid societal and technological changes, fear-based organizational climates can hinder teachers' willingness to express opinions and engage in constructive criticism, thereby fostering organizational blindness. Organizational dissent, defined as employees' expression of disagreements regarding organizational policies or practices, may serve as a counterbalance by enhancing awareness and preventing strategic errors. Conversely, organizational inertia, characterized by resistance to change and adherence to routines, can exacerbate organizational blindness. The study employed a correlational research design and collected data from 288 teachers working in state schools across various educational levels in Kilis, Turkey. Standardized scales were used to measure fear culture, organizational blindness, dissent, and inertia. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics, correlation analyses, and mediation testing using Hayes' PROCESS Macro (Model 4) with bootstrapping. Findings indicate that fear culture positively affects organizational blindness both directly and indirectly through increased inertia and decreased dissent. Specifically, organizational dissent partially mitigates, while organizational inertia reinforces, the impact of fear culture on organizational blindness. These results highlight the critical role of psychological safety, participatory management, and supportive school climates in fostering teacher engagement, promoting innovation, and reducing organizational blindness in educational settings. The study contributes to understanding the mechanisms through which fear culture influences school effectiveness and offers practical implications for educational leadership and policy.

Keywords: Organizational Dissent, Organizational Inertia, Fear Culture, Organizational Blindness, School

ÖZET

Bu çalışma, okullarda korku kültürü ile örgütsel körlük arasındaki ilişkide örgütsel muhalefet ve örgütsel ataletin aracılık etkilerini incelemektedir. Hızlı toplumsal ve teknolojik değişimlere uyum sağlamak zorunda olan çağdaş eğitim kurumlarında, korkuya dayalı örgütsel iklimler öğretmenlerin görüşlerini ifade etme ve yapıcı eleştiriye katılma isteğini engelleyerek örgütsel körlüğün ortaya çıkmasına zemin hazırlayabilmektedir. Örgütsel muhalefet, çalışanların örgütsel politika veya uygulamalara ilişkin görüş ayrılıklarını ifade etmeleri olarak tanımlanmakta olup, farkındalığı artırarak ve stratejik hataları önleyerek dengeleyici bir rol üstlenebilmektedir. Buna karşılık, değişime direnç ve rutinelere bağlılıkla karakterize edilen örgütsel atalet, örgütsel körlüğü daha da derinleştirebilmektedir. Araştırmada ilişkisel araştırma modeli kullanılmış ve Türkiye'nin Kilis ilinde farklı eğitim kademelerinde görev yapan devlet okullarındaki 288 öğretmenden veri toplanmıştır. Korku kültürü, örgütsel körlük, örgütsel muhalefet ve örgütsel atalet değişkenlerini ölçmek amacıyla standartlaştırılmış ölçekler kullanılmıştır. Verilerin analizinde betimsel istatistikler, korelasyon analizleri ve Hayes'in PROCESS Makrosu (Model 4) kullanılarak bootstrap yöntemiyle aracılık analizleri gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bulgular, korku kültürünün örgütsel körlüğü hem doğrudan hem de artan örgütsel atalet ve azalan örgütsel muhalefet yoluyla dolaylı olarak olumlu yönde etkilediğini göstermektedir. Özellikle örgütsel muhalefetin, korku kültürünün örgütsel körlük üzerindeki etkisini kısmen azalttığı, örgütsel ataletin ise bu etkiyi güçlendirdiği belirlenmiştir. Elde edilen sonuçlar, öğretmen katılımını artırmada, yeniliği teşvik etmede ve örgütsel körlüğü azaltmada psikolojik güvenin, katılımcı yönetim anlayışının ve destekleyici okul iklimlerinin kritik önemini vurgulamaktadır. Çalışma, korku kültürünün okul etkililiğini hangi mekanizmalar aracılığıyla etkilediğine ilişkin anlayışa katkı sunmakta ve eğitim liderliği ile politika yapıcılar için önemli uygulamaya dönük çıkarımlar sağlamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Örgütsel Muhalefet, Örgütsel Atalet, Korku Kültürü, Örgütsel Körlük, Okul

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly changing and transforming conditions, the sustainability of organizations depends on their ability to accurately perceive environmental changes and adapt to them in a timely manner (Çınar & Toker, 2019; Uçkan et al., 2013). However, organizations that adhere strictly to routine, remain excessively attached to existing ways of working, and resist change gradually struggle to recognize environmental signals, a phenomenon referred to in the literature as organizational blindness or organizational myopia (Aydın, 2019; Seymen et al., 2016). Organizational blindness is defined as the inability of organizations to adequately detect opportunities, threats, risks, and long-term changes in both internal and external environments, to identify errors in current methods and practices, and to develop sound forecasts for the future (Altınay et al., 2012; Döş, 2013). This condition is primarily driven by factors such as an excessive focus on short-term goals, overconfidence stemming from past successes, habits and routines, resistance to change, weak external relationships, non-participatory and autocratic management approaches, strict adherence to rules and the status quo, and a disengagement from learning and innovation at individual, organizational, and sectoral levels (Golembiewski & Munzenrider, 1988; Güzel & Sığircı, 2021; Levitt, 1960; Levinthal & March, 1993; Seymen et al., 2016). In organizations dominated by organizational blindness, employees tend to experience monotony, desensitization, and burnout; innovative ideas are suppressed, and organizational silence increases (Akar, 2025a; Czakon et al., 2023). Consequently, critical issues such as communication breakdowns, inefficiency, conflicts, loss of motivation, missed opportunities, and the weakening of sustainable competitive advantage emerge, rendering organizations ineffective and vulnerable in the face of environmental changes (Güzel & Sığircı, 2021; Kartal, 2018; Tushman & O'Reilly, 1996). In this context, organizational blindness represents a critical phenomenon that poses a significant threat to both current performance and long-term organizational survival (Kılıç, 2024).

As in other types of organizations, organizational blindness in educational institutions can weaken the ability to adapt to environmental changes and create significant obstacles. In this context, a comprehensive examination of organizational blindness is necessary to counteract it and mitigate or eliminate its negative effects. Identifying the factors that influence or contribute to the emergence of organizational blindness will enable more effective management of this issue. In particular, examining the impacts of elements such as a culture of fear, organizational dissent, and organizational inertia, as well as revealing their interactions, constitutes a critical step toward minimizing the adverse consequences of organizational blindness.

A culture of fear refers to an organizational and social climate in which individuals are unable to express their thoughts openly due to concerns about punishment, exclusion, or making mistakes, and where unconditional compliance with authority is emphasized (Cüceloğlu, 2008). The formation of this culture is largely influenced by managerial approaches that are authoritarian and punitive, often based on negative assumptions about human nature (Asunakutlu & Avcı, 2010; Kaşmer, 2009). The use of authority as a tool of pressure and low tolerance for errors are among the primary organizational factors that reinforce a culture of fear (Orhun & Meriç, 2019; Şahin, 2015). At the individual level, past experiences, personality traits, and fear of failure further strengthen this process (Oestreich, 1995; Oran & Akan, 2017). In organizations dominated by a culture of fear, criticism and questioning are suppressed, and employees tend to remain silent (Eren, 2005; Kish Gephart et al., 2009). This environment undermines employees' perceptions of psychological safety and increases organizational silence behaviors (Akar, 2025b). Employees who conceal their opinions experience decreased motivation and organizational commitment, and their creativity is limited (Ersü & Akar, 2023; Kavak, 2015). Moreover, levels of stress and burnout rise, while job satisfaction and organizational trust are adversely affected (Erdem, 2007; Topaloğlu & Ergan, 2014). Consequently, a culture of fear constitutes a structure that weakens individual development and organizational productivity, ultimately hindering sustainable success.

Another significant variable potentially related to organizational blindness is organizational dissent. Organizational dissent is defined as the expression of employees' disagreements regarding organizational decisions, policies, or practices (Kassing, 1997; Özdemir, 2010). The main factors that trigger dissent behaviors include how employees are treated, organizational change processes, the implementation of decisions, roles and responsibilities, resource allocation, unethical practices, and performance evaluations (Kassing & Armstrong, 2002; Ötken & Cenkcı, 2013). Additionally, employees' personality traits and intra-organizational interactions also influence dissent (Kassing & Armstrong, 2002). Organizational dissent can occur not only toward managers but also among employees themselves (Garner, 2013; Graham, 1986). Repressive and autocratic environments hinder the expression of dissenting views and negatively affect communication (Hegstrom, 1990; Naktiyok, 2019). Suppression of dissent can strengthen authoritarian structures and reduce innovation capacity (Pianesi, 2017; Shahinpoor & Matt, 2007). Conversely, when

dissent is constructively addressed, it enhances employee engagement, motivation, and performance while contributing to the resolution of intra-organizational issues (Bakan et al., 2019; Koçođlu Sazkaya & Tuđrul, 2022; Naktiyok, 2019). Employees who cannot express their opinions may resort to covert or external dissent, which can increase the risk of conflict (Garner, 2013; Nalbantođlu & Ulufer Kansoy, 2023). Furthermore, supporting organizational dissent strengthens an organization's learning and innovation capacities from its environment and helps prevent strategic errors (Pianesi, 2017; Stanley, 1981). Therefore, organizational dissent is considered a critical tool for both individual and organizational development (Zhan & Hample, 2016).

Another important concept to consider in the context of organizational blindness is inertia. From a psychological perspective, inertia is defined as individuals exhibiting behaviors such as passivity, reluctance, indecisiveness, laziness, and lack of purpose (Sekman, 2007). While this phenomenon begins at the individual level, it gradually spreads throughout the organization, preventing employees from fully realizing their potential, creating idle capacity, and resulting in productivity losses (Çankaya & Demirtaş, 2010; Kaya et al., 2018). Organizational inertia, on the other hand, refers to an organization's inability to adapt to changing environmental conditions, its rigid adherence to existing strategies, structures, and practices, resistance to innovation and change, and its failure to respond in a timely manner (Huff et al., 1992; Larsen & Lomi, 2002). Key drivers of organizational inertia include individual and organizational factors such as habits, routines, traditions, reluctance to learn, knowledge inertia, avoidance of uncertainty, and risk aversion, as well as bureaucratic and rigid organizational structures, organizational age and size, and overconfidence resulting from past successes (Atalay, 2013; Courtney et al., 1999; Hannan & Freeman, 1984; Kinnear & Roodt, 1998; Nelson & Winter, 1982; Sekman & Utku, 2009; Soysal, 2010). In organizations dominated by inertia, the capacity for innovation diminishes, environmental opportunities are inadequately leveraged, and competitive strength gradually declines (Atalay, 2013; Türkan & Esmer, 2019). During this process, weakened internal communication and reduced democratic participation lead to employee alienation, increased reluctance, and organizational cynicism, ultimately causing losses in productivity and performance, decreased job satisfaction, and higher turnover intentions, thereby seriously threatening the long-term sustainability of organizations (Özen Kutaniş & Dikili, 2012; Şahlan, 1979; Sekman & Utku, 2009; Soysal, 2010).

Educational institutions are dynamic entities that must adapt to societal and technological changes. In this process, issues such as organizational blindness may emerge. Organizational blindness can lead to insensitivity to changes and opportunities in both internal and external environments, resulting in overlooked problems within schools and losses in productivity. This phenomenon may be particularly pronounced in environments dominated by a culture of fear. In such settings, employees may struggle to express their ideas freely and may avoid criticism or making mistakes. This type of psychological climate can create fertile ground for the deepening of organizational blindness. Additionally, the suppression of organizational dissent and the increase of organizational inertia can hinder innovative approaches and foster resistance to change. Therefore, understanding the effects of a culture of fear on organizational blindness, as well as the mediating roles of organizational dissent and inertia in this interaction, is critical for the sustainable success of educational institutions. The findings may guide educational administrators in creating healthier organizational climates, enhancing teacher motivation, promoting innovative work behaviors, and strengthening schools' adaptive capacity. Moreover, these insights can facilitate the development of strategic approaches to prevent organizational blindness, contributing to more effective and efficient functioning of educational institutions. The research hypotheses are as follows:

- H1:** A culture of fear has a significant and positive effect on organizational blindness.
- H2:** A culture of fear has a significant and negative effect on organizational dissent.
- H3:** A culture of fear has a significant and positive effect on organizational inertia.
- H4:** Organizational dissent has a significant and negative effect on organizational blindness.
- H5:** Organizational inertia has a significant and positive effect on organizational blindness.
- H6:** Organizational dissent and organizational inertia mediate the effect of a culture of fear on organizational blindness.

2. METHOD

In this study, the mediating roles of organizational dissent and organizational inertia were examined in explaining the relationship between a culture of fear and organizational blindness. The research was conducted within the framework of a relational (correlational) research design. The correlational design is an approach aimed at revealing the mutual relationships between two or more variables and how these variables change together. In this context, this design focuses on determining the direction and strength of the relationships among the variables (Büyüköztürk et al., 2018).

2.1. Population and Sample

The population of the study consists of teachers working at different educational levels in public schools located in the central district of Kilis during the 2025–2026 academic year. The sample comprises 288 teachers who were selected using convenience sampling and voluntarily agreed to participate in the research. This sampling method allows the researcher to determine the most appropriate sample by taking into account limitations related to time, cost, and available resources (Balçı, 2015). The demographic data of the 288 teachers who participated in the study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Teachers Participating in the Study

Variable	Category	f	%
Gender	Male	135	46,9
	Female	153	53,1
Age Group	20-30 years	84	29,2
	31-40 years	93	32,3
	41-50 years	67	23,3
	51 years and above	44	15,3
School Level	Primary School	110	38,2
	Secondary school	104	36,1
	High school	74	25,7

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the teachers who participated in the study. Regarding gender distribution, 46.9% of the teachers are male, while 53.1% are female. In terms of age groups, 29.2% of the teachers are between 20 and 30 years old, and 32.3% fall within the 31–40 age range. Teachers in the 41–50 age group constitute 23.3%, and those aged 51 and above account for 15.3%. Regarding school level distribution, 38.2% of the participants work in primary schools, 36.1% in secondary schools, and 25.7% in high schools.

2.2. Data Collection Instruments

In the study, the Culture of Fear Scale was used to determine teachers' perceptions of a culture of fear, the Organizational Blindness Scale was employed to measure perceptions of organizational blindness, the Organizational Dissent Scale was utilized to assess perceptions of organizational dissent, and the Organizational Inertia Scale was applied to evaluate perceptions of organizational inertia.

2.2.1. Culture of Fear Scale: Developed by Çelik and Kahraman (2019), the Culture of Fear Scale consists of 18 items across three main sub-dimensions. The scale is designed to measure participants' perceptions using a 5-point Likert-type rating. Çelik and Kahraman (2019) reported a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.92 for the overall scale, indicating high internal consistency. In the present study, the reliability of the Culture of Fear Scale was re-evaluated, yielding a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.88, which demonstrates that the scale remains a highly reliable measurement tool in this context.

2.2.2. Organizational Blindness Scale: Developed by Seymen, Kılıç, and Kinter (2016), this scale was further tested for validity and reliability using data collected from educational institutions by Sezen-Gültekin (2019). The analyses confirmed the scale's structure, comprising 18 items and three sub-dimensions. Reliability analyses indicated an overall Cronbach's Alpha of 0.82. In the present study, the Cronbach's Alpha for the entire scale was calculated as 0.85, supporting the scale's robustness and consistency as a measurement instrument.

2.2.3. Organizational Dissent Scale: Developed by Kassing (1998) and adapted into Turkish by Dağlı (2015), the Organizational Dissent Scale contains 15 items across two main dimensions: vertical dissent and horizontal dissent. Participants' perceptions are assessed using a 5-point Likert-type scale. Reliability analyses conducted by Dağlı (2015) indicated an overall Cronbach's Alpha of 0.85, demonstrating high

internal consistency. In this study, the scale's reliability was re-tested, and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.84 was obtained, confirming that the scale is a reliable measurement tool.

2.2.4. Organizational Inertia Scale: Developed by Liao, Fei, and Liu (2008) and adapted into Turkish by Çankaya (2010), the Organizational Inertia Scale comprises 14 items and two main sub-dimensions: "Knowledge Inertia" and "Experience Inertia." Participants' responses are measured using a 5-point Likert scale. In this study, the overall Cronbach's Alpha of the scale was found to be 0.72, indicating that it is a reliable and consistent measurement instrument.

2.3. Data Collection and Analysis

For data collection, the measurement instruments were uploaded to Google Drive, and the links to these instruments were sent to the teachers via email. Participants were asked to complete and return the surveys within a two-week period. At the end of this period, a total of 288 teachers had responded, and the collected data were subjected to statistical analyses. The data analysis was conducted using the SPSS software package. In the first stage, descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentages) were calculated for the research variables, and correlation analysis was performed to examine the relationships between the variables. Subsequently, to determine the mediating roles of organizational dissent and organizational inertia in the relationship between a culture of fear and organizational blindness, the Process Macro developed by Andrew Hayes was employed. This tool allows analyses using various structural models suitable for the requirements of the study. For the purpose of testing the specified relationship, Model 4 was selected, which enables the simultaneous assessment of multiple mediation effects, thereby serving the objectives of the research. To examine the significance of indirect effects, 5,000 bootstrap samples were generated, and results were evaluated based on a 95% confidence interval. This procedure aimed to test the mediating roles of organizational dissent and organizational inertia in the relationship between a culture of fear and organizational blindness.

3. FINDINGS

Descriptive statistics and correlation coefficients regarding teachers' perceptions of culture of fear, organizational blindness, organizational dissent, and organizational inertia are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Values of Teachers' Perceptions of Culture of Fear, Organizational Blindness, Organizational Dissent, and Organizational Inertia

Variable	N	M	SD	1.	2.	3.	4.
1. Fear Culture	288	3.06	0.66	1			
2. Organizational Blindness	288	2.86	0.54	0.758**	1		
3. Organizational Dissent	288	2.93	0.70	-0.439**	-0.611**	1	
4. Organizational Inertia	288	2.73	0.84	0.329**	0.511**	-0.203**	1

p < 0.01

As shown in Table 2, considering the 5-point Likert scale, teachers' perceptions of all variables were evaluated at a moderate level based on mean scores. In terms of mean scores, teachers exhibited the highest mean perception in culture of fear (M = 3.06), followed by organizational dissent (M = 2.93) and organizational blindness (M = 2.86). The lowest mean perception was observed for organizational inertia (M = 2.73). These findings indicate that these factors have a certain impact within schools, although the effects are neither very strong nor weak. The results emphasize the importance of taking steps to improve school culture and structures. According to the correlation analysis, there was a strong positive relationship between teachers' perceived culture of fear and organizational blindness ($r = 0.758$, $p < .01$). This suggests that environments with higher levels of a culture of fear are likely to experience increased organizational blindness. A moderate negative relationship was observed between culture of fear and organizational dissent ($r = -0.439$, $p < .01$), indicating that in environments where a culture of fear is prevalent, dissent may decrease as employees are inhibited from expressing criticism or opposing views. Additionally, a low-to-moderate positive relationship was found between culture of fear and organizational inertia ($r = 0.329$, $p < .01$), suggesting that higher levels of fear may lead to increased inertia, with employees becoming more passive due to fear and uncertainty. Furthermore, a negative relationship was observed between organizational dissent and organizational blindness ($r = -0.611$, $p < .01$), indicating that higher levels of dissent reduce blindness and increase employee awareness. A positive relationship was also found between organizational inertia and organizational blindness ($r = 0.511$, $p < .01$), suggesting that in environments with higher inertia, organizational blindness may increase, as resistance to change can result in overlooked problems.

The model and analysis results regarding the mediating effects of organizational dissent and organizational inertia in the relationship between a culture of fear and organizational blindness are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Model of the Mediating Effects of Organizational Dissent and Organizational Inertia in the Relationship Between Culture of Fear and Organizational Blindness and Standardized β Values

As shown in Figure 1, the total effect of a culture of fear on organizational blindness is significant ($\beta_c = 0.758$; $p < .001$). The culture of fear has a significant negative effect on the mediating variable organizational dissent ($\beta = -0.439$; $p < .001$) and a significant positive effect on organizational inertia ($\beta = 0.329$; $p < .001$). The effects of the mediating variables on organizational blindness are also significant, with organizational dissent showing a negative effect ($\beta = -0.325$; $p < .001$) and organizational inertia a positive effect ($\beta = 0.272$; $p < .001$). When the mediating variables are included in the model, the direct effect of a culture of fear on organizational blindness decreases but remains significant ($\beta_c = 0.525$; $p < .001$), indicating that organizational dissent and organizational inertia play a partial mediating role. In other words, a culture of fear influences organizational blindness both directly and indirectly. Examining the R^2 values, a culture of fear explains 57% of the variance in organizational blindness ($R^2 = 0.57$). Its effect on organizational dissent accounts for 19% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.19$), and its effect on organizational inertia explains 11% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.11$). Moreover, when organizational dissent, organizational inertia, and a culture of fear are considered together, they account for 74% of the variance in organizational blindness ($R^2 = 0.74$). The total, direct, and indirect effects of a culture of fear on organizational blindness are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Total, Direct, and Indirect Effects of a Culture of Fear on Organizational Blindness

Effects / Paths	β	t	p	95% CI	R^2
Total Effect					
FC → OB	0.758	19.63	< .001	[0.661, 0.808]	0.57
Direct Effects					
FC → OD	-0.439	-8.26	< .001	[-0.571, -0.351]	0.19
FC → OI	0.329	5.89	< .001	[0.213, 0.427]	0.11
FC → OB	0.525	14.89	< .001	[0.442, 0.576]	
OD → OB	-0.325	-9.57	< .001	[-0.362, -0.239]	
OI → OB	0.272	8.40	< .001	[0.207, 0.334]	
Indirect Effects					
FC → OD → OB	0.143	—	—	[0.104, 0.183]	
FC → OI → OB	0.089	—	—	[0.056, 0.127]	

Note: FC = Fear Culture, OD = Organizational Dissent, OI = Organizational Inertia, OB = Organizational Blindness; 95% CI = 95% Confidence Interval

Table 3 summarizes the total, direct, and indirect effects of a culture of fear on organizational blindness. The direct effect of a culture of fear on organizational blindness is significant and strong ($\beta = 0.525$; $p < .001$), while the indirect effects occur through organizational dissent (FC → OD → OB; $\beta = 0.143$) and organizational inertia (FC → OI → OB; $\beta = 0.089$), both of which are significant. The total indirect effect is 0.232, which is smaller in magnitude compared to the direct effect. Notably, the indirect effect through organizational dissent contributes to the broader dissemination of the influence of a culture of fear on organizational blindness. These findings indicate that all proposed hypotheses (H1, H2, H3, H4, H5, and H6) are supported, demonstrating that a culture of fear affects organizational blindness both directly and partially indirectly through organizational dissent and organizational inertia.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study examined the effects of a culture of fear on organizational blindness from the perspective of teachers' perceptions, as well as the mediating roles of organizational dissent and organizational inertia in this relationship.

The findings indicate that teachers' perceptions of culture of fear, organizational blindness, organizational dissent, and organizational inertia are generally at a moderate level. In relative comparison among the variables, the highest perception was observed for culture of fear, while the lowest was for organizational inertia. This may be considered positive in the sense that a culture of fear has not become a dominant feature throughout the organization. However, the relatively higher perception of culture of fear compared to other variables suggests that teachers may occasionally experience concerns about punishment, exclusion, or negative evaluation in administrative processes. This perception may limit open communication and voluntary participation within the organization, leading teachers to be cautious in expressing problems or engaging in innovative behaviors. When the literature on the culture of fear is examined, the current findings show partial consistency with previous research findings. While some studies report low levels of perceived culture of fear among teachers (Ersü & Akar, 2023; Kahraman, 2019), similar low perception levels have also been reported among academics (Sincer, 2016). Conversely, other studies conducted with teacher samples have reported moderate levels of perceived culture of fear (Akar, 2025b). Similarly, regarding organizational blindness, the literature shows no consistent trend in teachers' perceptions, with some studies reporting low levels (Avcı, 2024; Soydan, 2022) and others reporting moderate levels (Akar, 2025a; Özateş, 2023). While many studies indicate high levels of perceived organizational dissent (Arayit, 2020; Arslan & Arslan, 2024; Doğan & Gökyer, 2025; İpek, 2020; Korucuoğlu, 2016; Yol & Zincirli, 2022), other research has reported moderate perceptions (Dağlı & Ağalday, 2015; Püsküllüoğlu & Altınkurt, 2018; Teski, 2017; Yaşa, 2018; Yalçın & Saygı, 2021). Regarding organizational inertia, studies indicate that teachers' perceptions of this phenomenon are generally reported at moderate to low levels. Some studies found moderate perceptions of organizational inertia among teachers (Doğru, 2024; Karayel, 2014; Özcan, 2023; Pasmaz, 2020; Yalçın, 2015), whereas others reported low perception levels (Karapınar Türkmenoğlu, 2023; Şaştım, 2019). Overall, these findings suggest that teachers' perceptions of organizational fear, blindness, dissent, and inertia may vary depending on organizational context, administrative practices, and individual characteristics of participants.

Correlation analyses indicated a strong and positive relationship between a culture of fear and organizational blindness, a moderate and negative relationship between a culture of fear and organizational dissent, and a low-to-moderate positive relationship between a culture of fear and organizational inertia. Additionally, a high-level negative relationship was observed between organizational dissent and organizational blindness, whereas organizational inertia exhibited a moderate and positive relationship with organizational blindness. These findings suggest that a fear-based organizational climate can weaken employees' tendencies to identify and question problems, limit the expression of critical opinions, and indirectly reinforce organizational inertia. Conversely, organizational dissent may serve a balancing function by enhancing organizational awareness through alternative perspectives and feedback. The results largely align with existing theoretical and empirical literature. In fear-based organizational climates characterized by low psychological safety and high concern for punishment, employees tend to avoid risk-taking, and the limitation of knowledge sharing and feedback behaviors can render errors, threats, and environmental signals invisible (Detert & Edmondson, 2011; Edmondson, 1999; Morrison & Milliken, 2000). This process may contribute to an increase in organizational blindness. Furthermore, the suppression of critical voice behavior and the weakening of organizational dissent by a culture of fear correspond with findings in the organizational silence literature, which emphasize that fear-based climates strengthen silent behavior (Akar, 2025b; Guo, Decoster, Babalola, De Schutter, Garba, & Riisla, 2018; Liang, Zhang, Feng, Huang, & Zhang, 2024; Morrison, 2014; Pinder & Harlos, 2001; Rashid & Rizvi, 2020). Moreover, in organizations dominated by fear and uncertainty, employees' tendencies to avoid risk and maintain existing practices may be reinforced (Gilbert, 2005; Hannan & Freeman, 1984; Levinthal & March, 1993). This can provide a psychological and structural basis for organizational inertia. Conversely, organizational dissent can reduce organizational blindness by supporting awareness, error detection, and learning processes. Organizational inertia, on the other hand, can reinforce organizational blindness through excessive adherence to routines and resistance to change (Atalay, 2013; Bakan et al., 2019; Koçoğlu Sazkaya & Tuğrul, 2022; Nemeth & Staw, 1989; Türkan & Esmer, 2019; Van Dyne & LePine, 1998).

The findings regarding the model testing indicate that a culture of fear has a strong and significant total effect on organizational blindness. When the mediating variables were included in the model, it was observed that a culture of fear exerts a negative and significant effect on organizational dissent and a positive and significant effect on organizational inertia. Furthermore, the effects of organizational dissent and organizational inertia on organizational blindness were also found to be significant. Mediation analysis results reveal that a culture of fear influences organizational blindness both directly and indirectly through organizational dissent and organizational inertia. The total indirect effect (0.232) being smaller than the direct effect indicates that these mediation relationships are partial. These findings confirm that all the hypotheses tested in the study are supported. Examination of R^2 values shows that a culture of fear explains organizational blindness most strongly, organizational dissent at a moderate level, and organizational inertia to a limited extent. Additionally, when organizational dissent and organizational inertia are considered together with a culture of fear, a substantial portion of organizational blindness can be explained. Overall, the study results highlight that a culture of fear plays a decisive role in increasing organizational blindness. This suggests that fear-based approaches in school management negatively affect organizational awareness and adaptability to change. Moreover, when the mediating variables are considered together with a culture of fear, a significant portion of organizational blindness can be accounted for. These results indicate that in fear-based organizational climates, employees' willingness to take risks and express critical opinions is weakened, organizational silence is reinforced, and organizational awareness and learning capacity may be limited (Akar, 2025b; Atalay, 2013; Detert & Edmondson, 2011; Durak, 2012; Edmondson, 1999; Koçoğlu Sazkaya & Tuğrul, 2022; Morrison & Milliken, 2000; Türkan & Esmer, 2019). Therefore, a culture of fear contributes to reduced organizational awareness and the reinforcement of rigid structures both directly and through mediation mechanisms, negatively affecting organizations' capacity to adapt to change and learn.

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- A school climate should be established where teachers can freely express their opinions and are not afraid to take risks.
- Mechanisms should be developed in decision-making processes that consider teachers' suggestions and criticisms.
- To reduce organizational inertia, innovative and flexible processes should be adopted instead of adherence to old practices.
- Fear-inducing management practices, such as punishment or exclusion, should be limited, and supportive and participatory management models should be preferred.

REFERENCES

- Akar, H. (2025a). The effect of psychological safety on organizational blindness among teachers: The mediating roles of organizational silence and innovative work behavior. In Ş. Koca (Ed.), *International academic research and studies in educational sciences* (1st ed., pp. 73–91). Serüven Yayınevi.
- Akar, H. (2025b). The impact of fear culture on teacher silence: The role of psychological safety. In S. Sönmez (Ed.), *Education sciences: Theory, methodology and practice* (pp. 79–97). Platanus Publishing. <https://doi.org/ISBN 978-625-6517-42-4>
- Altınay, A., Mercan, N., Aksanyar, Y., & Sert, S. (2012). İşletme körlüğü, silo sendromu ve çözüm önerisi olarak örgütsel zeka. *Organizasyon ve Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 4(1), 13–19.
- Arayit, E. (2020). *Öğretmenlerin örgütsel muhalefet davranışları ve işe yabancılaşma düzeyleri arasındaki ilişkinin bazı değişkenlere göre incelenmesi* [Yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi]. Gazi Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü.
- Arslan, Ş., & Arslan, S. (2024). Öğretmenlerin örgütsel muhalefet düzeyleri. *Ulusal Eğitim Toplum ve Dünya Dergisi*, 1(1), 20–42.
- Asunakutlu, T., & Avcı, U. (2010). Aile işletmelerinde nepotizm algısı ve iş tatmini ilişkisi: An investigation of the relationship between nepotism and job satisfaction in family businesses. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 15(2), 93–109.
- Atalay, M. (2013). *Kurumsal ataletin yabancılaşma ve işten ayrılma niyetine etkisi* [Yüksek lisans tezi]. Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.

- Avcı, T. (2024). *Öğretmenlerin algularına göre örgütsel DNA, örgütsel körlük ve örgütsel dayanıklılık arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi* [Yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi]. Recep Tayyip Erdoğan Üniversitesi, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü, Eğitim Bilimleri Anabilim Dalı.
- Aydın, A. U. (2019). *San kaynakları yönetiminde eğitim ve geliştirmenin örgütsel körlük ve örgütsel sessizliğe etkilerinde örgütsel öğrenmenin aracılık rolü: Turizm sektöründe bir uygulama* [Yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi]. Selçuk Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Seyahat İşletmeciliği ve Turist Rehberliği Ana Bilim Dalı.
- Bakan, İ., Doğan, İ. F., & Purlu, A. (2019). Örgütlerde iletişim tarzının çalışanların muhalif davranışları üzerindeki etkisi. *BMIJ*, 7(5), 2225–2247.
- Balcı, A. (2015). *Bilimsel araştırma yöntemleri* (21. bs.). Pegem Akademi.
- Büyüköztürk, Ş., Kılıç Çakmak, E., Akgün, Ö. E., Karadeniz, Ş., & Demirel, F. (2018). *Bilimsel araştırma yöntemleri* (26. bs.). Pegem Akademi.
- Courtney, H., Kirkland, J., & Viguerie, P. (1997). Strategy under uncertainty. *Harvard Business Review*, 75(6), 66–79. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10174798/>
- Cüceloğlu, D. (2008). *Korku kültürü: Niçin 'muş gibi' yaşıyoruz?* Remzi Kitabevi.
- Czakon, W., Klimas, P., Kawa, A., & Kraus, S. (2023). How myopic are managers? Development and validation of a multidimensional strategic myopia scale. *Journal of Business Research*, 157, 113573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.113573>
- Çankaya, H. İ. (2010). İlköğretim okul yöneticilerinin vicdan odaklı yaklaşım düzeyleri ile atalet algıları arasındaki ilişki. *Ahi Evran Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 11(2), 65–74.
- Çankaya, İ., & Demirtaş, Z. (2010). Öğretmen adaylarının görüşlerine göre üniversite iklimi ve atalet arasındaki ilişki. *Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 28(28), 1–9.
- Çelik, K., & Kahraman, Ü. (2019). Okullarda korku kültürü ölçeği: Geçerlik ve güvenilirlik çalışması. *İnönü Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 20(2), 319–333.
- Çınar, F., & Toker, K. (2019). Hastane yöneticilerinin stratejik yönetim araçlarını bilme ve kullanım düzeylerinin örgütsel inovasyona etkisi. *Turkish Studies – Social Sciences*, 14(5), 2117–2134. <https://doi.org/10.29228/TurkishStudies.36824>
- Dağlı, A. (2015). *Örgütsel muhalefet ölçeğinin Türkçe'ye uyarlanması: Geçerlik ve güvenilirlik çalışması*. *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 14(53), 198–218. <https://doi.org/10.17755/esosder.45359>
- Dağlı, A., & Ağalday, B. (2015). Öğretmenlerin örgütsel muhalefetin nedenlerine ilişkin görüşleri. *İlköğretim Online*, 14(3), 885–898. <https://doi.org/10.17051/ilo.2015.86261>
- Detert, J. R., & Edmondson, A. C. (2011). Implicit voice theories: Taken-for-granted rules of self-censorship at work. *Academy of Management Journal*, 54(3), 461–488. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2011.61967950>
- Doğan, C., & Gökyer, N. (2025). Ortaokullarda görev yapan öğretmenlerin pozitif psikolojik sermaye alguları ile örgütsel muhalefet alguları arasındaki ilişki. *Türk Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 23(2), 1499–1529. <https://doi.org/10.37217/tebd.1585992>
- Doğru, S. (2024). *Okul yöneticilerinin öğretimsel liderlik davranışları ile öğretmenlerin örgütsel ataletleri arasındaki ilişki* [Yüksek lisans tezi, Mersin Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü].
- Döş, İ. (2013). Örgütsel körlük ve okul. In 5. *Uluslararası Türkiye Eğitim Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metin Bildirileri Kitabı* (ss. 150–157). Çanakkale: Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart Üniversitesi.
- Durak, İ. (2014). Örgütsel sessizliğin demografik ve kurumsal faktörlerle ilişkisi: Öğretim elemanları üzerine bir araştırma. *Atatürk Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 28(2), 89–108.
- Edmondson, A. C. (1999). Psychological safety and learning behavior in work teams. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 44(2), 350–383. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2666999>
- Erdem, R. (2007). Korku kültürü–değerler kültürü: Kültürel çalışmalarda yeni bir boyut olabilir mi? XV. *Ulusal Yönetim ve Organizasyon Kongresi Bildiriler Kitapçığı*, 245–250.
- Eren, E. (2005). *Örgütsel davranış ve yönetim psikolojisi*. Beta Yayınları.

- Ersü, A. A., & Akar, H. (2023). Öğretmenlerin korku kültürü algılarının duygusal bağlılıklarına ve içsel motivasyonlarına etkisi. *Muallim Rifat Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 5(2), 275–295.
- Garner, J. T. (2013). Dissenters, managers, and coworkers: The process of co-constructing organizational dissent and dissent effectiveness. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 27(3), 373–395. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0893318913486440>
- Gilbert, C. G. (2005). Unbundling the structure of inertia: Resource versus routine rigidity. *Academy of Management Journal*, 48(5), 771–784.
- Golembiewski, R. T., & Munzenrider, R. H. (1988). *Stress in organizations: Toward a phase model of burnout*. Praeger.
- Graham, J. W. (1986). Principled organizational dissent: A theoretical essay. In B. M. Staw & L. L. Cummings (Eds.), *Research in organizational behavior* (Vol. 8, pp. 1–52). JAI Press.
- Guo, L., Decoster, S., Babalola, M. T., De Schutter, L., Garba, O. A., & Riisla, K. (2018). Authoritarian leadership and employee creativity: The moderating role of psychological capital and the mediating role of fear and defensive silence. *Journal of Business Research*, 92, 219–230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.07.034>
- Güzel, Ş., & Sığırcı, H. (2021). Örgütsel körlük kavramının içerik analizi yöntemiyle incelenmesi. 14. *Uluslararası Güncel Araştırmalarla Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi Tam Metinleri* (ss. 1031–1046). Dumlupınar Üniversitesi.
- Hannan, M. T., & Freeman, J. (1984). Structural inertia and organizational change. *American Sociological Review*, 49(2), 149–164. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2095567>
- Hegstrom, T. G. (1990). *Mimetic and dissent conditions in organizational rhetoric*. *Journal of Applied Communication Research*, 18(2), 141–152.
- Huff, J. O., Huff, A. S., & Thomas, H. (1992). *Strategic renewal and the interaction of cumulative stress and inertia*. *Strategic Management Journal*, 13(1), 55–75. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.4250131006>
- İpek, M. B. (2020). *Öğretmenlerin örgütsel muhalefet düzeyleri ile örgütsel sessizlik algıları arasındaki ilişki* [Yayınlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi], Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü
- Kahraman, Ü. (2019). *Okul yöneticilerinin yönetim tarzı, örgüt DNA'sı ve örgütsel değişimin okullardaki korku kültürüne etkisi* (Doktora tezi). Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü.
- Karapınar Türkmenoğlu, G. (2023). *Öğretmen ataleti ile okul yöneticilerinin liderlik stiline öğretmen performansına etkisi* [Doktora tezi], Marmara Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Eğitim Yönetimi ve Denetimi Bilim Dalı.
- Karayel, G. (2014). *Ortaöğretim öğretmenlerinin örgütsel atalet düzeyleri: Bayrampaşa ilçesi örneği* [Yayınlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi], Okan Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Eğitim Yönetimi ve Denetimi Anabilim Dalı.
- Kartal, N. (2018). *Örgütsel miyopinin hizmetkar liderlik ekseninde tahlili: Eğitim kurumları çalışanları üzerinde bir araştırma* [Yayınlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi]. Işık Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İşletme Yönetimi Bilim Dalı.
- Kassing, J. W. (1997). Articulating, antagonizing, and displacing: A model of employee dissent. *Communication Studies*, 48(4), 311–332. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10510979709368510>
- Kassing, J. W. (1998). Development and validation of the organizational dissent scale. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 12(2), 183–229. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0893318998122002>
- Kassing, J. W., & Armstrong, T. A. (2002). Someone's going to hear about this: Examining the association between dissent-triggering events and employees' dissent expressions. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 16(1), 39–65. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0893318902161002>
- Kaşmer, T. (2009). *Korku kültürünün yönetim, çalışanlar ve işletme üzerindeki etkilerinin analizi* [Yayınlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi]. Muğla Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İşletme Ana Bilim Dalı.

- Kavak, H. (2015). *İşletmelerde korku kültürü ve yönetimi: Adıyaman ili örneği* [Yayınlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi]. Türk Hava Kurumu Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İşletme Ana Bilim Dalı.
- Kaya, Ş. D., Yüceler, A., & Özen, M. Y. (2018). Hemşirelerde atalet davranışları ve hasta güvenliği. *Nobel Medicus Journal*, 14(2), 40-48.
- Kılıç, T. (2024). Development of organizational blindness scale. *Uluslararası Akademik Birikim Dergisi*, 7(3), 285–294. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401448>
- Kinncar, C., & Roodt, G. (1998). The development of an instrument for measuring organisational inertia. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 24(2). <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajip.v24i2.652>
- Kish-Gephart, J. J., Detert, J. R., Treviño, L. K., & Edmondson, A. C. (2009). Silenced by fear: The nature, sources, and consequences of fear at work. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 29, 163–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.riob.2009.07.002>
- Koçoğlu Sazkaya, M., & Tuğrul, E. (2022). *The moderating role of perceived supervisor support on the relationship between organizational dissent and intention to leave*. *Istanbul Management Journal*(93), 21–37. <https://doi.org/10.26650/imj.2022.93.002>
- Korucuoğlu, T. (2016). *Örgütsel güç oyunları ve örgütsel muhalefet arasındaki ilişki* [Yayınlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi], Eskişehir Osmangazi Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü.
- Larsen, E., & Lomi, A. (2002). Representing change: A system model of organizational inertia and capabilities as dynamic accumulation processes. *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, 10(5–7), 271–296. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1569-190X\(02\)00085-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1569-190X(02)00085-0)
- Levinthal, D. A., & March, J. G. (1993). The myopia of learning. *Strategic Management Journal*, 14(S2), 95–112. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.4250141009>
- Levitt, T. (1960). Marketing myopia. *Harvard Business Review*, 38(4), 45–56.
- Liang, Y., Zhang, Y., Feng, Y., Huang, Y., & Zhang, C. (2024). The impact of abusive supervision on nurses' organizational silence: The multiple linear mediation of psychological capital and fear. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*, 17, 4769–4779. <https://doi.org/10.2147/JMDH.S475793>
- Liao, S., Fei, W., & Liu, C. (2008). Relationships between knowledge inertia, organizational learning and organizational innovation. *Technovation*, 28(4), 183–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2007.11.005>
- Morrison, E. W. (2014). Employee voice and silence. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 1, 173–197. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-031413-091328>
- Morrison, E. W., & Milliken, F. J. (2000). Organizational silence: A barrier to change and development in a pluralistic world. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(4), 706–725. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2000.3707697>
- Naktiyok, S. (2019). Örgütsel muhalefet. In C. N. Karabey & G. Kerse (Eds.), *Örgütsel davranış düzleminde güncel kavramlar* (ss. 167–193). Gazi Kitabevi.
- Nalbantoğlu, C. B., & Ulufer Kansoy, S. (2023). *Measuring the perception of organizational dissent in manufacturing and service sectors*. *Akademik Hassasiyetler*, 10(21), 260–278. <https://doi.org/10.58884/akademik-hassasiyetler.1223397>
- Nelson, R. R., & Winter, S. G. (1982). *An evolutionary theory of economic change*. Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.
- Nemeth, C. J., & Staw, B. M. (1989). The tradeoffs of social control and innovation within groups and organizations. In L. Berkowitz (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol. 22, pp. 175–210). Academic Press.
- Oestreich, D. K. (1995). *Driving fear out of the workplace: Creating the high-trust, high-performance organization*. Jossey-Bass.
- Oran, Ç. F., & Akan, B. B. (2017). Akademisyenlerin örgütsel sessizlik algıları: Konuya ilişkin bir uygulama. *Kırklareli Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 6(5), 117–134.

- Orhun, B. N., & Meriç, S. (2019). Turizm işletmelerinde korku kültürü ve yönetimi. In F. Alaeddinoğlu, S. Özer, S. Şahin & H. Arslan Kalay (Eds.), *Turizm araştırmaları* (ss. 45–70). Paradigma Akademi.
- Ötken, A. B., & Cenkci, T. (2013). Beş faktör kişilik modeli ve örgütsel muhalefet arasındaki ilişki üzerine bir araştırma. *Öneri Dergisi*, 10(39), 41–51.
- Özateş, B. (2023). *Ortaöğretimde görev yapmakta olan öğretmen görüşlerine göre örgütsel körlük üzerine karma bir araştırma* [Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi], Recep Tayyip Erdoğan Üniversitesi, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü, Eğitim Bilimleri Anabilim Dalı.
- Özcan, B. (2023). *Beden eğitimi öğretmenlerinde ataletin yordayıcıları olarak algılanan örgütsel destek, iş yabancılaşma, veli yaklaşımı ve tükenmişlik* [Yayımlanmamış doktora tezi]. Mersin Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Anabilim Dalı.
- Özdemir, M. (2010). *Ankara ili kamu genel lise yönetici ve öğretmenlerinin örgütsel muhalefete ilişkin görüşleri* [Yayımlanmamış doktora tezi]. Ankara Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Eğitim Yönetimi ve Teftişi Bilim Dalı.
- Özen Kutanis, R., & Dikili, A. (2012). Değişim boyutuyla örgütlerde sinizm. D. E. Özler (Ed.), *Örgütsel davranışta güncel konular* (ss. 269–285). Ekin Yayınevi.
- Pianesi, A. (2017, December 14). Is organizational dissent important? The consequences of speaking up when you disagree at work. *Smart Brief Corporate Web Page*. <https://www.smartbrief.com/original/2017/12/organizational-dissent-important-consequences-speaking-when-you-disagree>
- Pinder, C. C., & Harlos, K. P. (2001). Employee silence: Quiescence and acquiescence as responses to perceived injustice. *Research in Personnel and Human Resources Management*, 20, 331–369. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-7301\(01\)20008-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-7301(01)20008-2)
- Pusmaz, H. Y. (2020). *Öğretmenlerin örgütsel atalet düzeylerinin yordayıcısı olarak örgütsel adalet algısı* [Yüksek lisans tezi], İstanbul Sabahattin Zaim Üniversitesi, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü, Eğitim Yönetimi ve Denetimi Anabilim Dalı.
- Püsküllüoğlu, E. I., & Altınkurt, Y. (2018). Öğretmenlerin eleştirel düşünme eğilimleri ile örgütsel muhalefet davranışları arasındaki ilişki. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 33(4), 897–914. <https://doi.org/10.16986/HUJE.2018037422>
- Rashid, M., & Rizvi, S. T. H. (2020). Impact of workplace bullying on employee creativity: Role of workplace fear, employee silence, and psychological capital. *RADS Journal of Business Management*, 2(2), 59–78.
- Sekman, M. (2007). *Kişisel ataleti yenmek* (12. basım). Alfa Basım Yayım Dağıtım.
- Sekman, M., & Utku, A. (2009). *Çevik şirketler: Kurumsal ataleti yenmek*. İstanbul: Alfa Yayınları.
- Seymen, O. A., Kılıç, T., & Kinter, O. (2016). Örgütsel körlüğün (örgüt miyopisi) ayrıntılı kavramsal analizi ve ölçümü: Geliştirilen bir ölçek yardımıyla değerlendirme. *Eurasian Academy of Sciences Social Sciences Journal*, 1, 212–222. <https://doi.org/10.17740/eas.soc.2016.MSEMP-18>
- Sezen-Gültekin, G. (2019). *Yükseköğretimde örgütsel körlük ve örgütsel sürdürülebilirlik arasındaki ilişkide örgütsel dayanıklılığın aracı rolü* [Yayımlanmamış doktora tezi]. Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi, Bolu, Türkiye.
- Shahinpoor, N., & Matt, B. F. (2007). *The power of one: Dissent and organizational life*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 74(1), 37–48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-006-9218-y>
- Sincer, S. (2016). *Öğretim elemanlarının algılarına göre korku kültürü ile tükenmişlik arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi* [Yüksek lisans tezi], (Hacettepe Üniversitesi, Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü).
- Soydan, B. (2022). *Okullarda örgütsel yenileşmenin bir yordayıcısı olarak örgütsel körlük* [Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi], Yıldız Teknik Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Eğitim Bilimleri Anabilim Dalı
- Soysal, A. (2010). Atalet: Etkin yönetim için kişisel ve örgütsel düzeyde bir analiz. *Çimento İşveren Sendikası Dergisi*, 24(3), 16–26.

- Stanley, J. D. (1981). Dissent in organizations. *Academy of Management Review*, 6(1), 13–19. <https://doi.org/10.2307/257136>
- Şahin, D. (2015). *Presenteeism (İşte var olamama) ile algılanan örgütsel destek, korku iklimi ve çalışmaya tutkunluk arasındaki ilişki: Hemşirelere yönelik bir araştırma* [Yayınlanmamış doktora tezi]. Trakya Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Şahlan, G. (1979). Bürokratik sistemlerde yönetime katılma olgusu ve yapısal sınırlılıklar. *Amme İdaresi Dergisi*, 12(2), 19–32.
- Şaştım, Z. (2019). *Öğretmenlerin algılarına göre atalet ve tükenmişlik düzeyleri arasındaki ilişki* [Yüksek lisans tezi], Uşak Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Teski, A. (2017). *Okul yöneticilerinin liderlik tarzları ile öğretmenlerin örgütsel muhalefet alguları arasındaki ilişki* [Yüksek lisans tezi], Uşak Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Eğitim Bilimleri Anabilim Dalı.
- Topaloğlu, C., & Ergan, S. (2014). Turizm işletmelerinde korku kültürü ve yönetimi. In Ş. A. Tükeltürk, N. A. Perçin, & B. Güzel (Eds.), *Turizm işletmelerinde çalışan ilişkileri yönetimi* (pp. 223–239). Detay Yayıncılık.
- Tushman, M. L., & O'Reilly, C. A. (1996). Ambidextrous organizations: Managing evolutionary and revolutionary change. *California Management Review*, 38(4), 8–30. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41165852>
- Türkan, A., & Esmer, Y. (2019). Örgütsel atalet kavramına teorik bir bakış. *Stratejik ve Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 3(3), 525–534. <https://doi.org/10.30692/sisad.616334>
- Uçkan, C. G., Latif, H., & Öztürk, Ö. F. (2013). İşletmelerde yönetici adayı havuzu yöntemiyle, yönetici adaylarının belirlenmesi (THY uygulaması). *Ejovoc - Electronic Journal of Vocational Colleges*, 3(3), 36–46.
- Van Dyne, L., & LePine, J. A. (1998). Helping and voice extra-role behaviors: Evidence of construct and predictive validity. *Academy of Management Journal*, 41(1), 108–119. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256902>
- Yalçın, S., & Saygı, E. (2021). Ortaokullarda görev yapan öğretmenlerin psikolojik dayanıklılık, örgütsel muhalefet ve örgütsel sessizlik alguları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. *Anadolu University Journal of Education Faculty*, 5(4), 402–426. <https://doi.org/10.34056/aujef.928300>
- Yalçın, S. A. (2015). The relationship between inertia and organizational change management: An application in educational institutions. *The Journal of Academic Social Science*, 3(20), 260–270.
- Yaşa, R. (2018). *Liselerde görev yapan öğretmenlerin görüşlerine göre örgütsel özdeşleşme ile örgütsel muhalefet arasındaki ilişki* [Yüksek lisans tezi], Yıldız Teknik Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Eğitim Bilimleri Anabilim Dalı.
- Yol, Ö., & Zincirli, M. (2022). Öğretmen algılarına göre örgütsel muhalefet ve örgütsel dışlanma arasındaki ilişki. *İnönü Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 23(3), 1898–1920.
- Zhan, M., & Hample, D. (2016). Predicting employee dissent expression in organizations: A cost and benefit approach. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 30(4), 441–471. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0893318916635752>